

"Secret Knowledge" of Folk Medicine in Uzbekistan: on the Example of Khorezm Region

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Abstract: The article is based on local written sources, scientific works of European, Russian and Central Asian researchers related to this topic, documents of the World Health Organization, state legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the protection of human health and preservation of historical and cultural heritage, students of Urganch State University during 1992-2022. It was prepared based on the results of the field-ethnographic practice and the author's personal observations.

Keywords: Ethno medicine, "secret knowledge" of folk medicine, magical powers and imaginations, classification.

Introduction

In many countries, occult healing is restricted. For example, according to statistics, 36% of Russians in Russia believe in magic, one in four respondents said that they use homeopathy for treatment. 5% of respondents said that they believe in psychics and healers (Anastasia Barvinskaya. 2022). However, in Article 50 ("Folk Medicine") of the Law of Russia "On Protection of Citizens' Health" adopted in 2011, it is stated that "folk medicine does not include occult-magic treatment methods (treatment through religious rituals)" (Federal Law "Ob osnovakh okhrany zdorovya grajdan v Rossiyskoi Federatsii" 2011: Article 50). In Austria, it is accused of fraud if non-scientific treatment methods are used, for example, "magic water" treatment (Maddalena S. 1999). In the legislation of some countries, it is said that those who are treated by "secret knowledge" of folk medicine are not insured.

In Uzbekistan, the actions of healers by means of magic are treated as fraud in the criminal code. Depending on the level of endangering human life and causing economic damage, they serve a prison term of 50 to 600 times the basic salary, or 1-3 years in correctional columns, and 3-8 years in severe cases. Healers with the secret knowledge of folk medicine are often located in historical-architectural monuments, according to which the responsibility for illegal activity in such objects, any damage caused to the object is established (Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 20021, a collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2016). Despite the established legal measures and prohibitions, it exists among the people. Even though they are regulated by state laws, they are not strictly controlled. On the contrary, secrecy is strong in relation to them. Indeed, the issue of "secret knowledge" of folk medicine is important due to its connection with human health treatment and healing practices, preservation of cultural monuments and spiritual heritage, religious worldviews of peoples, social and family relations in society, and its scientific research is an urgent issue. The population of the region we are studying is the object that uses the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine the most.

The level of study of the project, theoretical-methodological foundations and research methods

The study of the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine and ritual specialists, places of treatment and methods of this field as a special social institution was first carried out in the field of anthropology, ethnography and folklore studies of Europe in the 20th century (EEEvans-Pritchard. 1994, M. Douglas. 1970. 2000, J. Foster, 1972). In the 21st century, with the increasing attention to folk medicine, the use of "secret knowledge" of folk medicine in different peoples of Russia began to be researched (L.I.Nikonova. 2024, N.E. Mazalova. 2019, T.V. Pashkova. 2018) , G.S. Popovkina. 2016).

This topic and object has its own perspective because it has not been studied in Uzbekistan in the aspect we have chosen. Therefore, it is necessary to disclose the reasons for not studying the topic. First, Uzbekistan lived in the former USSR for many years. In this society, any form of religion was limited and even permeated with atheistic worldviews (and the issue of "secret knowledge" of folk medicine is closely related to various forms of religion and belief). Secondly, the issue of "secret knowledge" of folk medicine is an extremely closed issue for the people themselves. It is a great social institution, but a closed, sacred and secret institution. Its disclosure or scientific research creates a number of difficulties in social relations for local scientists. A third reason for the lack of research is the nature of "secret knowledge" (the use of supernatural methods or magic to harm and heal people). Fourthly, disclosure and prohibition of the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine can cause unexpected difficulties and protests (social-political-economic-religious). After all, there is a societal need for "secret knowledge" and thus the social order towards magic remains very strong.

Although the places of treatment through the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine have not been studied scientifically in the aspect we have chosen, they are studied by historians, archaeologists as a historical-cultural monument, by architects as an architectural structure, by geographers, naturalists, by theologians and philosophers in the religious aspect, and by folklorists as a folk art. , studied by medical personnel from the point of view of traditional folk medicine. Until 1995, it was studied a lot by ethnographers engaged in descriptive-ethnographic research. After the independence of Uzbekistan, the religious worldviews of the people were defined in articles 18, 29, 31, 61 of the constitution, which corresponded to the mentality of the Uzbek people, and freedom in matters such as faith, justice, religion, charity. From this period, a wide path was opened for the development of folk medicine, which was under persecution before. Anthropologists, representatives of the medical field, psychologists, neurophysiologists began to take a more or less serious approach to the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine in their research. Local authors and people interested in the history of the country published many pamphlets.

When presenting the review of literature related to this topic, we found it acceptable to group them. 1. Local written sources 2.***It was written in the second half of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century***Works of European and Russian researchers. 3. ***Works of researchers of the Soviet Union era*** 4. ***Scientific studies created after 1990.***

1. Local written sources.All the written sources available in Central Asia can provide material for this topic. Because in the Islamic world, holy places and their features, stories, legends and narratives about famous saints and their blessings are popular. They have become a part of everyday life. The Great Silk Road, which connected the regions from China to Rome, was also a source of information exchange. It should also be noted that until the beginning of the 20th century, treatment in Uzbekistan, namely in Khorezm, was based on folk medicine.

We will not talk about all sources, but we will list the most important ones. In the sources written in Arabic-Persian and Turkish languages of the 10th century, folk medicine and its various fields were approached from a scientific point of view. In this regard, it is possible to list the works of Abu Rayhan Beruni "Monuments left from ancient peoples", "Minerology", "Geodesy" and "Saydana". In the part of the author's work "Relics of Ancient Peoples" entitled "About the Feasts of the Khorazmians", "Prophets and Pretenders to Prophethood", "Pre-Paganism Iranian Feasts and Holidays"(Beruni. 1957)we will find examples related to the topic. In his work "Minerology" we will get acquainted with the properties of stones and their role in human health, the magical conditions associated with stones and their use in

treatment through the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine, beliefs, superstitions and their untruths and compatibility with their experiments.(Beruniy. 2017).The author empirically analyzed the persons and actions related to witchcraft existing among the peoples at that time. His work "Saydana" dedicated to folk medicine serves as a guide for medical representatives to this day. In this work, the thinker mentions many events related to folk medicine, medicinal plants, and their importance in the treatment of diseases.

In all volumes (consisting of 4 volumes) of the famous doctor of the East, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, "The Laws of Medicine", folk medicine, types and causes of diseases, their treatments, methods of treating the body and soul (psychotherapy, body movement therapy, art therapy in folk medicine) and doctors from them we will see scientific information about how to use it (Abu AliIbn Sina. 2020)

Abu Abdullah Yaqut ibn Hamawi, a Rab traveler, also talks about the places of pilgrimage in Khorezm and the reasons and procedures for visiting them in his work "Mo'jam ul-buldan". In his work, the author mentions that the graves of famous people of the Islamic world have become places of salvation for people (Elmurodov I., Eshmurodov M. 2005).

In the Middle Ages, people's healing places and famous people who were referred to in various diseases and difficulties were described in tazkiras. For example, Tazkiranavis Fariddin Attar's "Tazkirat ul-Avliya"." (Fariddin Attar. 2013)In the work, it is mentioned about several saints of Khorezm, such as Sultan Uwais Qarani (626-657) and Yusuf Hamadani (1048-1138), who were famous in the Khorezm oasis, and about their divine power to cure people's diseases.

Also, in Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani's work "Maqamati ul-Yusuf Hamadani" (Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani. 2003), if information is given about the life activities of his teacher Sheikh Yusuf Hamadani and his attitude towards his students, it is said that Ibn Battuta is one of the most revered saints in Central Asia - the tomb of Najmuddin Kubra in Khorezm. and asserts that it is the center of a mystical order. Ibn Batuta notes that even though the dog is a symbol of loyalty among Muslims, it is usually not sanctified, but "the pilgrims, even if they are 'old Muslims', do not reject the ancient narratives about the dog of Najmuddin Kubra." We exist in Khorezm through this work of his related to the dog We look for the roots of magical healing.(Ibrahimov N. Ibn Battuta and his journey to Central Asia... - B.58-59).Already, in the mythology of ancient Khorezm, the dog occupies an important place, and the people still use the magical healing methods associated with it.

"Nasayim-ul Muhabbat" by Alisher Navoi(Alisher Navoi. 1968)In his work, several saints are described in detail, Sultan Uwais and Yusuf Hamadani shrines, rituals there, and valuable information about healing methods. Alisher Navoi considered it acceptable to train specialist doctors so that the people's knowledge of medicine would not go to waste, and he established medical and medical centers, schools and madrasas in Astrabad and other cities called "Ash-shifa", "Dorush-shifo", "Maskani Olimon" and schools and madrasahs. and tried to create conditions for the work of judges.

In the written sources of the end of the 17th - beginning of the 20th century, the description of the oasis shrines and the conditions in them, the attention to the treatment of diseases in this period is found in the works of local historians and poets such as Abulghazi Bahadirkhan, Muhammad Erniyozbek oglu Ogahi, Shermuhammad Munis and Bayani. For example, Abulghazi Bakhodirkhan"Manofe'ul-insan>("Things useful for human health", 1657)The work consists of four parts, in whichAbulgaziThe names of more than 105 diseases and their treatment methods have been explained very well. There is no area of medicine that is not covered in this book. Of course, diseases are not given according to a certain system, they are written as surgical, therapeutic, obstetric-gynecological, therapeutic or pediatric or other diseases, and their treatment methods are indicated (Sabirov R. 1995). We see many innovations and originality in his work. The author studied each disease without blindly following tradition. Despite being the khan of Khiva and a great physician, Abulgazi kept astrologers in his palace and worked based on their predictions. Sometimes he himself used occult-magical methods of treatment. His"My family is Turkish" in the workValuable information is provided about the attitude of the Khans of Khiva to the shrines (Abulghazi.1992). Indeed, one of the main functions of shrines at that time was a place for healing.

The history of Khans in the works of Ogahi and Munis "Firdavs ul-Iqbal" (Garden of Happiness) and "Shahidul Iqbal", along with socio-political events, the perfect reverence for the saints and the holy places where they are buried is covered in detail. The semantics of the magical healing places sanctified by people such as Ismomut Baba shrine in Takhta (Republic of Karakalpakstan), Najmuddin Kubro in Kokhna Urganch (Republic of Turkmenistan), Hakim father's mausoleum in Kungiro, Sheikh Mukhtar Vali in Akmasjid village located in Yangiarik and turned into places of healing can be obtained from the works of these authors (Shermuhammad Munis, Muhammadrizo Agahi. 2010). Similar information can be obtained from the "Khorazm trip diaries" of the Iranian ambassador Mohammad Alikhan Gafur, who was in Khorezm in early 1842 (Muhammad Ali Khan Gafur. 2005)

In 1852, during the reign of Mohammad Aminkhan, Mirzo Rizaqulikhan Hidayat-Loloboshi, who was an ambassador from Iran to Khiva, wrote "Safarnomai Khorazm" about various situations (for example, places for the treatment of the disabled and mentally ill) in the shrine of Pahlavon Mahmud. Khudaiberganov K. 2009).

The poet and historian Syed Hamid Tora Kamyab, who belongs to the generation of Khiva Khan, in his work "Tawarikh ul-Havonin" Umar Eshon, Sadiq Eshon, Yusuf Khan Eshon, Ibadullah Eshon (from Chotko'frukli), Islamkhoja Eshon (from Qataghan), Uzbek Siddiq Makhzum, are among the leaders and representatives of Sufism in Khorezm. While giving information about Sayyid Abdullah, Muhammadsharif from Hazara, Ulugjan Eshan from Ghaziabad, and his son Babajon Makhzum, he calls them to the palace, gives them a feast, and then talks in the mosque. Syed Hamid Tora Komyob. 2002. – B. 99–107). Already, in Khorezm, most of the pirs and eshons are people who heal with magic words.

Khudoyberdi Koshmuhammad's son Khivaqi, who lived in Khiva in the 19th century, wrote "Dili Gharayib", which has reached us, along with information about Khiva, about the saints who lived in the oasis and their different dwellings. (The tomb of Sayyid Alauddin Khivaqi inside the city of Khiva, 300 great mashaikhs around it, Hazrat Sheikh Abul Wafai Khorazmi (15th century) outside the city and a thousand other sheikhs around him, 200 steps from the southeast of the city, Sheikh Husayn Baba, the Eyed Father and four from the city wrote down the information about the burial of sixty noblemen located a thousand steps away, as well as the murids of Najmuddin Kubra named Muhammad). Similar information can be found in the book "Riyaz al-Zakirin" written by Allahyar ibn Khudoyberdi at the beginning of the 20th century (Mahmudov J. 2017). In fact, the population visited all the above-mentioned shrines to heal from various diseases.

2. The second half of the 19th century - the works created by the researches of the Russian Empire and some European countries at the beginning of the 20th century. In the works created by orientalists, ethnographers, historians, artists, scientists, local historians and military topographers who came to the Khiva Khanate during the Russian Empire, there is a lot of information about the life and history of the cities of Khorezm, customs and rituals of the local population, pilgrimage sites, as well as folk medicine and its settlements. Europeans using modern medicine are amazed at the variety of diseases available here and the methods of their treatment. In their works, they wrote that Khiva, one of the most prominent states of the Middle Ages, had no doctors or institutions that served to restore health except for azaimkhan, duakhan, and fortune teller. However, they do not take into account the lack of attention to science in Central Asian khanates destroyed by mutual feudal wars. It is worth mentioning that in the works of the Hungarian A. Vamberi, it is noted that in the Khiva Khanate it was possible to make a lot of money with prayer, and magic was used in the treatment of diseases from the simplest to the most complex ones (Vambery A. 2003).

Ophthalmologist Blankennagel, who came to Khiva in 1793, tried to treat the types of glaucoma that were common among the inhabitants of this place. According to his memoirs, he received 40-50 patients every day and had a reputation among the people. During this period, local residents who were cured of their illness sought to deify the healer. (Путевые заметки майора Бланкеннагеля о Хиве. Поездка сего из Оренбурга в Хиву 1793–1794 гг. 1858)

L. who was in Khiva in 1873. Kostenko, in addition to illuminating the architecture of the Pahlavon

Mahmud mausoleum, which was one of the most famous places of spiritual healing of that time, the mosque also reserved a place for the sick, orphans, blind, disabled, deaf and dumb, etc. they make a living at the expense of their funds", he wrote (Kostenko L. 1873)

While studying the places of treatment through the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine, information about their semantics was obtained from A. Kalmykov (Kalmykov A.1908), who came to the Khiva khanate in the beginning of the 20th century, about Mazlum Khan Suluv's mausoleum and the shrines of Sheikh Husayn Baba, M. Ivanin's (Ivanin M., 1873) about sanctified places such as Hazrat Polvan ata, Ismamud ata, Ayat ata and Tokmok ata, A.L. We also used Kun's information about saint Qambar Baba, Sheikh Najmiddin Kubro's mausoleum, Hakim father's mausoleum and the religious ceremonies performed here dedicated to healing (Kun A. 1876).

Academician V., who objectively covered many pages of the Khorezm oasis history In addition to interesting comments about shrines and saints in his works, Barthold also provides information about the mentally ill and the disabled. (Barthold W., 1964).

German scientist K. In Zaleman's research, special attention is paid to the mythological rituals of the people of Khorezm. In his article dedicated to Sheikh Hakim father (Sulayman Bakirgani), who is famous in Central Asia, he writes about the worship of Hubbi, the son of the sheikh, and mentions that "Worship of Hubbi", "rescuing drowned people and giving life to slaughtered oxen" were widespread in ancient Khorezm. (Zaleman K., 1898)

It should be noted that in the second half of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, in the reports, memoirs and scientific works written by ambassadors, soldiers, merchants, travelers, and scientists who came to the Khiva Khanate, the features of the shrines of the Khorezm oasis as a place of healing were written in the method of ethnographic description, and the legends recorded in these works is of particular importance for work.

2. Analysis of scientific research on the historiography of the Soviet Union period.

The study of the subject of "secret knowledge" of folk medicine, treatment methods and places through it acquired a unique character during the Soviet Union. Because, during this period, scientific research in social sciences was carried out within the framework of society's ideology and politics. The topic we chose was considered "superstition" in the politics of that time. However, it cannot be denied that the fundamental views on the analysis of this issue, which plays an important role in the daily life of Khorezm residents, have also been stated. In this regard, the scientific research conducted by archaeologists, ethnographers, architects and art historians carried out theoretical-methodological studies in the study and illumination of the history, ethnography of the Khorezm oasis. For this reason, we have divided the scientific works of this period into archaeological, ethnographic, folkloristic, architectural,

Archaeological research. In fact, the Khorezm issue received more attention during the Soviet regime. The largest research in this regard is still the work of the Khorezm archeological-ethnographic expedition organized in the 30s of the 20th century. Dozens of works of S.P. Tolstov, leader of the expedition, such as "Ancient Khorezm", "In Search of Ancient Khorezm Culture", "Along the Ancient Oks and Yaxart Rivers" can be the theoretical and methodological basis for this topic. In particular, in his book "Ancient Khorezm" "The Way of Corribants", a bright synthesis of ethnographic, historical, archaeological and linguistic methods is noticeable in solving the religious problems of Khorezm residents (Tolstov. S.P., 1948). Among the archaeologists, in the works of Ya.G. Ghulomov, Sultan Uvais, Suleiman Haddadi, Said Ota, Arolcha Avliyo, Sheikh Mukhtar Vali, The history of Ismamut father shrines and interesting information about their construction are recorded. In the work, the scientist touched on the history, construction and naming of cemeteries, which are the basis of shrines, but the place of cemeteries as a place of treatment in the daily life of the people was not shown (Gulomov Ya.G., 1959). Although the main historical-archaeological and scientific works of A.S. Sagdullaev, M. Mambetullaev, Q. Sobirov were created on the basis of archeological materials, some of their studies deal with the issues of religion, religious rituals and customs performed in the field of health care and treatment. mentioned. however, the

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Ethnographic studies.In the 30s of the 20th century, ethnographers carried out extremely active research work at TXAEE. In particular, the work created on the basis of field research by K.L. Zadykhina, who led the northern detachment of the expedition, contains scientifically based considerations related to the religious beliefs and rituals of the inhabitants of the oasis. His "Пережитки возрастных классов у народов Средней Азии" in the article "We tried to solve the issues of our chosen topic in connection with primitive religions (Zadykhina. K., 1951). Yu.V. Knazorov's article "Shamun-Nabi Mazar" is also devoted to the historical-ethnographic analysis of issues related to human health in Khorezm (Knazorov Yu.V., 1949). K.A. Inostrantsev. In the work "O domusulmanskoy kulture Khivinsky oazisa" the issues of "secret knowledge" related to folk medicine practiced among the inhabitants of the oasis are analyzed by means of historical-comparison on the example of traditions and secrets (K.A. Inostrantsev. 1877). We can continue the list of scientific studies of ethnographers for a long time. However, we can fit only some of them into the scope of the project. Yu.V. Rapoport, A.V. Tokarev, V.N. Yagodin, N.P. Lobacheva, V.N. Basilova, S. Demidova, T.A. Zhdanko, O.A. Sukhareva, M.S. Andreeva's research is directly related to this topic related. In their works, they analyzed the use of "secret knowledge" of the people of Khorezm in terms of folk medicine as a ritual or traditional ritual related to clothing, housing, funeral and wedding ceremonies. Magic issues were considered a thing of the past. However, they did not recognize the application of the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine, that it is their centuries-old experience, that it contains real treatment methods, or that there are people with unique abilities. However, the works of the above-mentioned scientists serve us as a methodical guide in the historical-ethnographic analysis of the selected project.

Ethnographer G.P. Snesaryov is one of the scientists who made a great contribution to the study of customs and rituals in the ethnography of Khorezm residents. Unlike other ethnographers of the Soviet era, he tries to show that orthodox Islam's dogmatics, mythology, and official traditions have merged with the archaic religions of the Muslim world, i.e., they have syncretized. He tries to theoretically justify the concepts of primitive religion on the basis of the materials he has collected. The author evaluates some issues in the life of the peoples of Central Asia as the remnants of primitive religions, and not as old things. G.P. Snesaryov in his works shows that magical people, magical animals and magic, as well as fantastic elements in the layer of objects, have already taken place in the layer of magical tales. (Snesaryov G.P. 2018). However, the scientist in his direct observations is surprised by some of the results of magic and witchcraft treatment and emphasizes that the result of any magic is aimed at health, peace and protection. G.P. Snesaryov analyzed the existing shrines in Khorezm and the rituals held in them from an ethnographic aspect, analyzed the architectural structure, attributes of the shrines, and the narratives related to them. Analyzing the narratives in the work "Under the sky of Khorezm" (Snesarev G.P., 1973), the scientist came to the conclusion that among the shrines in Khorezm, the mausoleums of Sufis stand out and they have a special respect. On issues such as his religious beliefs and the cult of saints, the principles of approach to ethnographic phenomena serve as a methodical guide for us.

According to the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine, treatment centers are also classified according to their names. a) Named after the names of the prophets whose names are mentioned in the Holy Quran, b) related to the names of the companions and their followers, who are famous in the Islamic world, c) treatment centers related to the saints and their blessings, g) related to the names of the martyrs, d) related to chiltons ("Qirq Chiltonlar" in the village of Mukhamon, Hazorasp district, "Qirq Chiltonlar Gosh" on

the southern side of the Qironch Baba cemetery (Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language. 2008), e) treatment centers associated with the names of various famous women who lived in history (Gullibibi, Mushkulkushad, Bibi Fatima) , Anbar ona and Bibi Hajar) , j) treatment centers associated with the names of various professional patrons.

Such places in Khorezm are also classified according to their specialization. a) Magical places for treating mental illnesses, b) Magical places for treating infertility, c) Magical places for treating occupational diseases.

In such places, "the following methods of healing through secret knowledge are used: getting spiritual strength - that is, getting the strength that can be given to him from God through saints, healing through the forgiveness of sins, beating or making me drink, performing charitable works (darveshana, charity, etc. k), by lighting a lamp at the saint's grave, tying a piece of one's handkerchief or a torn piece of one's clothes to a tree, a tree, hugging trees, warming oneself by fire, rolling in the soil, drinking water from holy wells and springs, thereby purifying oneself or getting rid of illness, eating ritual food to prepare, to be divinely healed by making an offering to a saint.

Summary

Studies show that the population uses the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine in the most difficult times, that is, in diseases for which medicines cannot be found. Otherwise, they use it more in places where the population has little medical education, in places far from medical centers and pharmacies, when they live in a difficult economic situation, and in places where their religious beliefs are not strong. They imagine the saints as mediators and patrons, intercessors before God. That is why they visit holy places and worship them. Pilgrimage rituals include the veneration of nature cults associated with the belief in the role of the spirits of ancestors, saints, and clerics as guarantors between God and people. This made people believe that living nature, environment, trees, fauna and, in general, living nature embodied the spirit, spirit and cult of ancestors. Of course, this is the result of the perception of people's beliefs and the human factor. For this reason, there is a belief among the population that trees, wells and plants associated with the shrine are considered sacred, and people who spit into wells, break trees or find plants will get sick. Population of water, air, fire, earth, they believe in divine communication with trees and animals. They are considered to be the cause of diseases and also their healers.

It should be said that folk medicine allows regional research of "secret knowledge", research of folk traditions and customs, and methods not fully known to science. It contains all the achievements from the first stage of human history to the present. For example, if the doctor's work tools reflect the development of the craft, their rights and obligations, liability for wrongful treatment serve to determine the legal literacy of the society.

It should be emphasized that the historical-architectural buildings in Khorezm, where the tombs of representatives of the Sufi order of Islam are located, play an important role in treatment through the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine. In fact, when it comes to treatment with Quranic verses or the existence of magic in Islam, the majority of the population still claims to use the "secret knowledge" of folk medicine. In addition, the still powerlessness of man in front of nature, traditions and ceremonies ensure the viability of this knowledge.

If we take 100% of the total discoveries on earth, 98% of them are about the material world. Only 2% is about the spiritual world of a person. Therefore, the spiritual world of a person requires serious research.

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